

On a new technical error in a further Reply by Oberlack et al.
and its far-reaching effect on their original study
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M. Frewer^{1*}, G. Khujadze² & H. Foysi²

¹ Trübnerstr. 42, 69121 Heidelberg, Germany

² Chair of Fluid Mechanics, Universität Siegen, 57068 Siegen, Germany

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Abstract

In the Response [J. Math. Phys. 57, 034103 \(2016\)](#) recently published to our Comment [J. Math. Phys. 57, 034102 \(2016\)](#), we will disclose a technical error which was not recognized during the peer-review process. This error has a far-reaching negative effect when trying to generate invariant solutions for the multi-point moments as proposed in their original study, Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013), which, despite the several corrections done in the Reply according to our Comment, remains to be flawed in the physical interpretation of its results.

1. Introduction

In the course of correcting in Section III the connection between the translational invariance of the multi-point moments and a particular invariant transformation of the Hopf functional, a new (technical) error has been made in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016). Unfortunately, this error was not detected by the Referees during the review process. However subtle, this error can be easily checked as explained below in Section 2. Ultimately, this error leads to wrong recursive assumptions in the dependency structure of all freely choosable integration functions f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n , with the unwanted effect that the corresponding invariant solutions for all multi-point moments (as presented in the original article Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013)) globally evaluate to zero for all times $t > 0$. This will be shown in Section 3.

2. Disclosing the technical error

The problem is that the result in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) on p.3 after Eq.(12), namely the conclusion that function f_2 should obey the constraint $f_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k - k')$, cannot be obtained from the internal integral relation Eq. (10) as claimed, but rather, if this functional property is required, has to be assumed from the outside. In other words, this constraint is not a necessary constraint, but an optional one.

This problem has its origin in the mistake that an identity relation is misleadingly treated as an equation. Note that, in going from Eq.(10) to Eq.(12) is just a mere change of representation by using different integration coordinates of the same mathematical object,

*Email address for correspondence: frewer.science@gmail.com

namely the integral expression for the constant C_2 . Such a change, obviously, cannot account for any constraint or restriction in the integrand f_2 , which itself, as the functions $z(k)$, can also be chosen arbitrarily in Eq. (10) (up to the natural constraint $f_2^*(-k, -k') = f_2(k, k')$, given by one of the internal Hopf constraints; see Eq. (108) in the original article Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013)). To be mathematically explicit, let's repeat their derivation in combining all steps into one single expression

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_2 &= \frac{1}{t^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_2(k, k') z(k') z(k - k') dk dk' \\ &\stackrel{(i)}{=} \frac{1}{t^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_2(k_1, k_1 - k_2) z(k_1 - k_2) z(k_2) dk_1 dk_2 \\ &\stackrel{(ii)}{=} \frac{1}{t^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_2(k, k - k') z(k') z(k - k') dk dk', \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.1)$$

which shows that we are only confronted with an identity relation in different representations: Equality (i) is based on the change of variables $(k, k') \mapsto (k_1 = k, k_2 = k - k')$ with Jacobian $|J| = 1$, and equality (ii) on the fact that k_1 and k_2 are just dummy variables, which can be renamed again to k and k' , respectively. Although this identity relation (2.1) must hold for all possible functions z , we *cannot* conclude now that $f_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k - k')$, simply because the function f_2 itself, independent of the choice for z , can be chosen arbitrarily as well (up to single constraint mentioned above).

Such an argumentation would only be correct, for example, if we were confronted with an equation to be solved for, e.g., if we would have an integral equation of the form

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(y(x), y'(x)) z(x) dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(y(x)) z(x) dx, \quad (2.2)$$

which should hold for all possible $z(x)$, then we can conclude that $F(y(x), y'(x)) = G(y(x))$.[†] But the combination or comparison of Eq. (10) and Eq. (12) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) does not lead to an equation. Instead, it only leads to a chain of identities in different representations as presented in (2.1). To make here the same conclusion as for an equation, namely to compare the transformed integrands, is definitely wrong.

A simple example makes clear this point: Since f_2 in the first line of (2.1) can be chosen arbitrarily (up to the natural constraint $f_2^*(-k, -k') = f_2(k, k')$, as was already mentioned above), let's choose it conformably, e.g., as a real symmetric function of the following form: $f_2(k, k') = \exp(-k^2 - k'^2)$. Then, if we would follow the reasoning of Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), according to their global result $f_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k - k')$, we would have to conclude that $\exp(-k^2 - k'^2)$ must be equal to $\exp(-k^2 - (k - k')^2)$, for all k and k' , which obviously is not correct; while on the other hand, to choose any f_2 such that it already obeys this constraint from the outset, would be too restrictive, as we will show in Section 3.

Hence, in the end this proves that the functional property $f_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k - k')$ is just an assumption introduced from the outside, and that it's *not* an internal consequence as claimed in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016). The same also holds true for all relations of f_3 given therein after Eq. (12). Important to note here is that, since we did not make use of any such assumptions in our Comment (Frewer *et al.*, 2016a), our result given through Eq. (20) is more general than the one considered in their Reply or original article.

[†]Also, if we have a definition in form of an integral expression, e.g. $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(x) z(x) dx \stackrel{\text{def.}}{:=} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) z(x) dx$, which should hold for all possible $z(x)$, then it's obvious that we can also define $F(x) \stackrel{\text{def.}}{:=} f(x)$. Note that if a coordinate transformation is performed on any such integral definition, it must be performed on *both* of its sides; similar to the case when any integral equation is being transformed.

3. The effect on the invariant multi-point solutions

Although not prohibited from the outset, to nevertheless make the external assumptions

$$f_2(k, k') = f_2(k, k - k'), \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$f_3(k, k - k', k'') = f_3(k, k' - k'', k''), \quad f_3(k, k', k'') = f_3(k, k'', k'), \quad (3.2)$$

as required on p. 3 after Eq. 12 in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), is not constructive, since they inevitably will only lead to unphysical results. For example, when considering spatially homogeneous multi-point solutions, as derived and discussed in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013) through Eqs. (129)-(131), we would obtain, with these assumptions (3.1)-(3.2), the unphysical result of a globally constant two-point correlation function in Eq. (131) being zero for all times $t > 0$.

To see this, let's re-derive Eqs. (129)-(131) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013), but now with the corrections and assumptions as presented in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) for the invariant functional solution of Eq. (7)

$$\Phi = 1 + C_1 + C_2 + \dots + C_n + \dots, \quad (3.3)$$

where, respectively, the corresponding functional relations for f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are given by Eq. (13) and Eq. (14) as[†]

$$f_1(k) = -2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k' f_2(k, k - k') dk', \quad (3.4)$$

$$f_2(k, k') = -3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k'' f_3(k, k' - k'', k'') dk''. \quad (3.5)$$

To generate spatially homogeneous multi-point solutions from the integration functions f_n , the following ansatz in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013) has been made (see their advisement between Eqs. (128)-(129))

$$f_n(k, k', \dots, k^{(n-1)}) =: \delta(k) F_n(k', \dots, k^{(n-1)}), \quad (3.6)$$

which for the first three elements reads as

$$f_1(k) = \delta(k), \quad f_2(k, k') = \delta(k) F_2(k'), \quad f_3(k, k', k'') = \delta(k) F_3(k', k''). \quad (3.7)$$

Since the delta-function $\delta(k)$ is defined as a real function, we recursively obtain the intermediate result through relations (3.4)-(3.5) that f_1 , f_2 and f_3 must be real functions then too, due to the fact that k , k' and k'' are all defined as real numbers. According to Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2013), the one-point moment in physical space, based on its corrected Fourier-form Eq. (15) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016), is then given as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u(x, t) \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \hat{v}(k, t) \rangle e^{ikx} dk \\ &= -\frac{i}{t} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_1(k) e^{ikx} dk, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

[†]Note that since Eq. (13) and Eq. (14) in Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2016) constitute integral equations which should hold for all possible functions z , the integrands can obviously be equated to (3.4) and (3.5), respectively.

and the two-point moment, based on its corrected Fourier-form Eq. (16), then as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle u(x, t)u(x', t) \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle \hat{v}(k, t)\hat{v}(k', t) \rangle e^{ikx+ik'x'} dkdk' \\ &= -\frac{2}{t^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_2(k+k', k') e^{ikx+ik'x'} dkdk'. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Now, let's rigorously examine the relations (3.4)-(3.5), based on the assumptions (3.1)-(3.2) and the ansatz (3.7):

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(k) &= -2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' f_2(k, k-k') \\ &= -2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' \delta(k) F_2(k-k') \stackrel{(i)}{=} -2\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' F_2(-k') \\ &\stackrel{(ii)}{=} 2\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' F_2(k'), \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

where equality (i) is due to that $\delta(k)$ only gives a contribution at $k=0$, while (ii) is based on a change of the integration variable. But since the function f_1 , due to assumption (3.1), can also be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(k) &= -2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' f_2(k, k-k') \\ &= -2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' f_2(k, k') = -2\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk' k' F_2(k') \\ &\stackrel{(3.10)}{=} -f_1(k), \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

we obtain the global result that $f_1(k) = 0$, for all k . This result then leads to a zero one-point moment (mean field) in (3.8), which is consistent to the fact that for a spatially homogeneous statistical field its one-point moment is zero.[†] Note that from this result $f_1(k) = 0$, we can further conclude that $F_2(k')$ must be at least a symmetric function $F_2(k') = F_2(-k')$, an information, which we also could have obtained by just equating both equations (3.10) and (3.11), and then comparing their integrands.

Continuing the investigation for relation (3.5), we first have to observe that the ansatz function F_3 (3.7), due to (3.2), will satisfy the corresponding conditions[‡]

$$F_3(-k', k'') = F_3(k' - k'', k''), \quad F_3(k', k'') = F_3(k'', k'). \quad (3.12)$$

Hence, relation (3.5) can either be written as

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(k, k') &= -3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' f_3(k, k' - k'', k'') \\ &= -3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' \delta(k) F_3(k' - k'', k'') \stackrel{(iii)}{=} -3\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' F_3(-k', k''), \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

[†]In general, from a statistically in space homogeneous velocity field $u(x, t)$, it follows a mean velocity $\langle u \rangle = u_0$ which is uniform in space and time, due to the defining mean field equations; with an appropriate choice of frame, however, $\langle u \rangle$ can be taken to be zero.

[‡]Note that since the delta-function $\delta(k)$ in (3.7) only gives a contribution at $k=0$, we obtain with this ansatz the equivalence $f_3(k, k-k', k'') = f_3(k, -k', k'')$.

or, according to (3.1), equivalently as

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_2(k, k') &= f_2(k, k - k') = -3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' f_3(k, k - k' - k'', k'') \\
 &\stackrel{(iv)}{=} -3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' \delta(k) F_3(-k' - k'', k'') \stackrel{(v)}{=} -3\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' F_3(k', k'') \\
 &\stackrel{(vi)}{=} 3\delta(k) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dk'' k'' F_3(k', -k''), \quad (3.14)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the equalities (iii) and (v) are based on the first condition in (3.12), equality (iv) on the fact again that the delta-function only contributes at $k = 0$, and equality (vi) due to changing the integration variable. Comparing now the integrands of equation (3.13) with those of (3.14), we obtain the following global result (for all k' and k'')[†]

$$F_3(-k', k'') = F_3(k', k''), \quad \text{and} \quad F_3(k', -k'') = -F_3(k', k''), \quad (3.15)$$

that is, F_3 must be a symmetric function in its first and antisymmetric in its second argument. But since F_3 , according to the second condition in (3.12), also must be a symmetric function when its two arguments get interchanged, one thus can only avoid a contradiction if F_3 itself is zero.[‡] But if $F_3 = 0$, then $f_3 = 0$ and then, according to (3.5), also $f_2 = 0$, which then finally leads to the unphysical result

$$\langle u(x, t)u(x', t) \rangle = 0, \quad (3.16)$$

of a globally zero two-point correlation function (3.9) for a (mostly non-Gaussian) random field $u(x, t)$, which itself should be statistically homogeneous in space and non-zero. This unphysical result will then propagate through all higher order multi-point moments. Although we explicitly revealed the incompatibility of the assumptions (3.1)-(3.2) only to the invariant solution (3.3), we confidently can expect that also the second invariant solution Eq. (107) in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2013) will be incompatible to these assumptions.

4. Conclusion

Despite the corrections done in the Reply (Waławczyk & Oberlack, 2016) according to our Comment (Frewer *et al.*, 2016a), their original study, Waławczyk & Oberlack (2013), remains to be flawed in the physical interpretation of its results:

Firstly, the new assumptions wrongly derived in the Reply for f_2 and f_3 inevitably lead to unphysical (globally zero) solutions for all multi-point moments in a recursive manner.

Secondly, the conclusions given e.g. on p.11 after Eq. (88), or on p.18 in Waławczyk & Oberlack (2013), are physically invalid, because they all are drawn from the wrong assumption that $z(0) = 0$ refers to a zero mean velocity. Unfortunately, our corresponding remark R4-(iii) in Section III of our Comment, which exactly points to this problem, has not been fully acknowledged. Instead, it is downplayed as a minor issue in that their formulations around these physical conclusions are only vaguely claimed as being “imprecise” (Waławczyk & Oberlack, 2016, p. 2), although being in a position of knowing better.

[†]Note that the second (antisymmetric) result in (3.15) is *not* obtained by just comparing (v) and (vi) in (3.14) alone, which also would be wrong as discussed in Section 2. Instead, this result has its correct origin in the comparison $-F_3(-k', k'') = F_3(k', -k'')$ between equations (3.13) and (3.14), which is equivalent to $-F_3(k', k'') = F_3(k', -k'')$ when using the already established first (symmetric) result in (3.15).

[‡]Because of having the chain: $F_3(k_1, k_2) = -F_3(k_1, -k_2) = -F_3(-k_2, k_1) = -F_3(k_2, k_1) = -F_3(k_1, k_2)$.

Third and lastly, determining statistical symmetries of a dynamical system which emerges from a deterministic description without investigating their transformational relation to those underlying deterministic equations, as was done throughout Waławczyk & Oberlack (2013), and also in all of their later studies, carries the high risk to operate with symmetries which may violate the principle of cause of effect. In particular the symmetries as shown again in the Reply, namely Eq. (4) for $c_1 = c_2 = 0$ and Eqs. (5)-(6) for $c_1 = 0$, are exactly such unphysical symmetries, in that they show an (invariant) effect on the statistical level but without having any (mostly non-invariant) cause on the deterministic level from which these statistical effects can emerge. For a more elaborate discussion on this problem, we refer, for example, to our recent review (Frewer *et al.*, 2016b).

References

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